

Fe K-edge X-ray Absorption Spectroscopy study of nanosized nominal magnetite.

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Abstract

When studying nominal magnetite nanoparticles it is mandatory to obtain a precise structural characterization to get an accurate relationship with their physiochemical properties. The great deal of information accumulated to date on the characterization of nominal magnetite and maghemite NPs does not clarify if the synthesized materials are single or multiphase systems involving bulk-like stoichiometric oxides (Fe_3O_4 , $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$, $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$,...) or single or multiphase entities formed by non-stoichiometric oxides. In this work we propose a new approach to determine the structure of Fe oxide NPs by using the Fe K-edge X-ray absorption near edge spectroscopy. We report here an X-ray absorption near edge spectroscopy study at the Fe K- and $\text{L}_{2,3}$ -edges on nominal magnetite nanoparticles synthesized by different methods. In addition, X-ray magnetic circular dichroism was recorded at the Fe $\text{L}_{2,3}$ -edges in selected samples. We have found that the experimental spectra are not well reproduced by any linear combination of the absorption spectra of Fe_3O_4 and $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ bulk references, even taking into account other oxides as goethite or ferrihydrite. The analysis of the Fe K-edge XANES spectra shows that is the size, and not the synthesis method, which determines the structure of the NPs. Our experimental results indicate that, irrespective of the synthesis method, the nominal magnetite NPs are, actually, a single phase non stoichiometric $\text{Fe}_{3-\delta}\text{O}_4$ oxide. At the origin of this phase are the cation vacancies, which lead to the modification of the structural arrangements at the Fe sites with respect to those found in bulk-like iron oxides.

Keywords: Magnetite nanoparticles, Magnetic oxides, XAS, XANES, XMCD.

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INTRODUCTION

Magnetic nanoparticles (NPs) are nowadays the subject of extensive research because of their promising applications in many technological areas.¹ The possibility of using NPs as nanodiagnostic or nanotherapeutic tools centers a great interest in the biomedical field.² In particular, iron oxide, in the form of magnetite (Fe_3O_4) and/or maghemite ($\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$), has been revealed as an ideal material because of its biocompatibility and easy removal from the body after its use following natural routes.³

The structural and physicochemical properties of the nanoparticles determine to a great extent their biofunctionality, being these properties associated with the average particle size, size distribution, shape, crystal order, surface properties, and the presence of bonded molecules at the surface. Similarly, the dependence of the magnetic properties of iron oxide nanoparticles on different parameters as the degree of structural order at the surface and inside the particles, has been also reported.⁴ However, despite these parameters can be controlled, in principle, with the synthesis method,^{4,5} the current description of these relationships is still rather vague. In this way, obtaining a precise characterization of these structural details in monodisperse nanocrystals, as a previous step to get an accurate relationship with their magnetic properties, is nowadays one of the most challenging open issues in the field.

This is of particular relevance in the case of monodisperse iron oxide nanocrystals. The great deal of information accumulated to date on the characterization of magnetite and maghemite NPs does not clarify if the synthesized materials are single or multiphase systems involving bulk-like oxides (Fe_3O_4 , $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$, $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$...), or multiphase entities formed by non-stoichiometric oxides.⁶⁻⁹ Very often the characterization of iron oxide magnetic nanoparticles is made by combining infrared (IR) and Mössbauer spectroscopies with X-ray diffraction (XRD) and transmission electron microscopy (TEM).^{10,11} However, the standard methods that we have for solving the atomic

structure of bulk crystals fail for such materials due to nanoscale effects arising from the inherently very small crystallite sizes, the large surface-to-volume ratio, near-surface relaxation, local lattice distortions, etc., broadening and smearing out the Bragg reflections in the XRD patterns or the Mössbauer lines.¹² This renders critical in the case of magnetite and maghemite nanoparticles as they may show structural disorder that can substantially modify the properties of the materials and, consequently, they cannot be simply considered as small pieces of bulk material. In addition to this, the existence of several polymorphs and their possible transformation through oxidation makes this problem further complicated. While the conversion of magnetite to maghemite on micron- or close-to-micron-sized particles has been well characterized, the same does not hold for ultrafine magnetite powders for which several Mössbauer experiments indicate the occurrence of partial oxidation including the formation of non-stoichiometric phases.^{7-9,13,14} Similarly, controversial results regarding the capability to distinguish Fe_3O_4 from $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ have been also reported when both IR or Raman spectroscopies have been used to characterize the samples.¹⁵⁻¹⁹ Finally, it is worth to mention that no general consensus exists regarding the oxidation mechanism of magnetite. The magnetite to hematite transformation has been proposed either to proceed directly or through the conversion of magnetite to maghemite and the subsequent conversion to hematite.^{18,20-23} Moreover, it has been also reported that magnetite seems to oxidize to maghemite via short-live "hydroxo" intermediate.²⁴

These uncertainties make clear that more powerful experimental tools are needed to obtain an accurate structural and magnetic characterization of these iron oxide NPs. These tools include X-ray absorption near-edge spectroscopy (XANES), extended X-ray absorption fine structure (EXAFS), and magnetic X-ray circular dichroism (XMCD). Early studies by van Aken *et al.* proposed different methods to obtain the quantification of ferrous/ferric ratios in minerals at submicrometre scale by analyzing the intensity ratio of the Fe $L_{2,3}$ -edge XAS spectra.^{25,26} In principle, the $L_{2,3}$ -

edges XAS spectral shape may provide information about the oxidation state and the symmetry of the Fe transition metal ions, and XMCD at these absorption edges allows to separate the contributions of the magnetic moments of Fe ions in tetrahedral and octahedral sites.^{25,27,28} However, for the most common iron oxides (γ -Fe₂O₃, Fe₃O₄, α -Fe₂O₃, FeO(OH),...) the L_{2,3}-edges XAS spectra are very similar. Therefore, upon the coexistence of several iron oxide phases in the same material, the possibility of extracting accurate quantitative information about the structural composition of the material gets complicated. Likewise, the L_{2,3}-edge XMCD for γ -Fe₂O₃ and Fe₃O₄ are very similar and, therefore, the possibility of making a fine analysis is seriously concerned when several phases are present in the sample. Besides, the presence of antiferromagnetic oxides, as α -Fe₂O₃ or FeO(OH), may also affect the normalization of the XMCD signals. Indeed, the analysis of the XMCD spectra of magnetite Fe₃O₄ centers a hot debate that extends to the dissimilarity of the reported experimental spectra.^{29–34} Recent XMCD studies performed at the Fe L_{2,3}-edges on 5 nm magnetite nanoparticles synthesized by different methods suggested the presence of up to 50% of maghemite.³⁵ This is in contrast with the 20% estimates obtained from Mössbauer spectroscopy on the same samples.³⁶ Beyond this quantitative disagreement, these works agree into suggesting the simultaneous presence of both magnetite and maghemite in the samples. Accordingly, the possibility of obtaining pure stoichiometric magnetite for particle sizes below a few tens of nanometers is seriously concerned, in agreement with the early work of Park *et al.*²⁹ These authors suggested that magnetite and maghemite form a mixture in the form $(\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3)_{1-x}(\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4)_x$, in such a way that maghemite is the dominant phase of the small 5-nm iron oxide nanocrystals, whereas the proportion of the magnetite component gradually increases as the particle size does. Unfortunately, these experiments did not determine if this mixture corresponds to a multiphase Fe₃O₄ + γ -Fe₂O₃ system in which each component retains its bulk properties or, on the contrary, we stand in front of a non-stoichiometric phase whose magnetic properties cannot be simply derived from the values

of bulk Fe_3O_4 and/or $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$.

This uncertainty in the phase determination prevents from establishing a definitive correlation between the magnetic properties and the nanostructure details of the iron oxide NPs. Very often it is assumed, making a parallel to the case of metal/oxidized iron NPs,³⁷ that the structure of iron oxide nanoparticles consists in a core of magnetite while the surface is partially oxidized. This leads to the proposition of different core-shell models ranging from a simply bulk-like magnetite-maghemite core-shell structure^{6,38} to others including a magnetic core and a nonmagnetic shell, where the magnetic dead layer should account for the observed decrease of the magnetization of the nanoparticles as compared to the bulk materials.³⁹ However, the variation of the shell thickness with the particle size is controversial,^{40,41} as it is the fact that for decreasing particle size below 50 nm the Verwey transition is no longer observable.⁴² Consequently, it renders clear the need of obtaining a precise determination of the nanostructure details of the iron oxide NPs prior to account for their magnetic properties. Hence, we propose in this work a different approach to determine the structure of Fe oxide NPs. We have performed a XANES study at the Fe K-edge in several magnetite/maghemite NPs synthesized by different methods. Our main objective is to determine if the nominal Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles are single or multiphase systems and the nature of these phases. More specifically, if the different components can be regarded as well defined, stoichiometric, bulk-like oxides or, on the contrary, they consist of non-stoichiometric oxides.

Fe K-edge X-ray absorption spectroscopy (XAS) has been widely used for the analysis of iron speciation in complex natural mixtures such as soils and sediments.^{43–45} In contrast, few studies have exploited the powerful characteristics of the XAS at the Fe K-edge for determining components and their relative proportions in magnetite and maghemite nanoparticles.^{46,47} The main advantage of using Fe K-edge absorption instead of that at the $L_{2,3}$ -edges for such a structural determination is twofold. Firstly, the Fe K-edge spectral shape is more sensitive to the geometrical

details of the absorbing site (overall symmetry, distances and bond angles) than the Fe $L_{2,3}$ -edge absorption, which is mainly governed by the point symmetry at the absorbing site (octahedral and tetrahedral in this case). In addition, for a similar coordination, there is a chemical shift of about ~ 3 -4 eV between Fe^{3+} and Fe^{2+} XANES spectra which is easily experimentally detected.⁴⁸⁻⁵¹ Secondly, the probing depth at the $L_{2,3}$ edges of iron is typically of ~ 45 Å in the case of iron oxides.⁵² Consequently, contribution from the atoms at the surface is emphasized in the absorption and dichroism signals at these edges. The K-edge spectra, on the other hand, probe the whole nanoparticle.⁴⁶ Therefore, by tuning the XAS absorption at the Fe K-edge it should be also possible to monitor how the relative amount of the different oxide phases, if present, varies with both the preparation method and the size of the particles.

EXPERIMENTAL

The iron oxide nanoparticles were obtained using different wet synthesis methods of common use in nanotechnology, namely precipitation, coprecipitation and thermal decomposition. It is worth to notice that the wet chemical procedures for synthesizing iron oxide nanoparticles allow a significant control over size and composition of the final product that grants their use in different applications.⁵³ Likewise, Roca *et al.*⁵⁴ have reported that thermal decomposition and coprecipitation methods produce nanoparticles within the same size range (3-18 nm), being spherical, isolated and nearly monodisperse in the case of thermal decomposition.

Samples obtained using the precipitation technique were synthesized diluting a mass of iron (II) sulfate heptahydrate ($FeSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$, >99% Sigma-Aldrich) in milli-Q water (Millipore) at pH 7 using NaOH and potassium nitrate (KNO_3 , Sigma-Aldrich) as mild oxidant.⁵⁵ With this method, iron oxide magnetic nanoparticles with mean D_{XRD} of 29 and 31 nm were synthesized. These samples were termed M29 and M31 respectively.

The coprecipitation process involves the joint hydrolysis of iron (II) and iron (III) salts in alkaline conditions. For synthesis, 4.4 g of iron (III) chloride hexahydrate ($\text{FeCl}_3 \bullet 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, >98% Sigma-Aldrich) and iron (II) chloride tetrahydrate ($\text{FeCl}_2 \bullet 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, >98% Sigma-Aldrich) were placed in 61 mL of milli-Q water, which was previously deaerated using Ar gas flow. The obtained solution was further purged with Ar gas to prevent oxidation of Fe^{2+} ions. After purging for 60 min, a volume of a 2M-NaOH solution was added dropwise up to pH 9 and observing the change in suspension's color to dark brown and further black.⁵⁶⁻⁵⁸ The black iron oxide product responded to magnetic fields as expected. Nanoparticle sizes were tuned after adjustments in the concentration of alkali and mixed iron salts for synthesizing iron oxide magnetic nanoparticles with mean D_{XRD} between 4 and 7 nm. These samples were labeled M4, M6 and M7.

The thermal decomposition procedure has been applied for the synthesis of spherical nanoparticles and briefly consists in the use of metal-organic and organometallic iron precursors in organic environments and in the presence of surfactants. Iron oxide nanoparticles of 7, 9, 12 and 18 nm in meansize (labelled M7D, M9D, M12D and M18D, respectively) were synthesized by thermal decomposition of iron organic compounds in organic solvents in the presence of surfactants. Different solvents were chosen for tuning the particle size.⁵⁹ Finally, magnetite transformation to maghemite was triggered after synthesis using a thermal treatment in air at 150 °C for 24 h. Materials termed G7D, G29 and G31 were obtained from the thermal oxidation of M7D, M29 and M31 respectively.

Magnetic nanoparticles and nanocomposites were imaged in a 200-keV FEI Tecnai T20 transmission electronic microscope to study their size, polydispersity and shape. To prepare the samples for this technique, one drop of a dilute suspension of nanoparticles dispersed in ethanol was placed on a carbon coated copper grid and allowing the solvent to evaporate slowly at room temperature. Mean particle size was calculated from TEM data obtained by measuring the largest internal di-

mension of at least 150 particles. X-ray patterns were collected at room temperature between 10° and 80° in a Rigaku D-Max system. The X-ray system was working at 40 kV and 100 mA with a counting rate of 4 s step^{-1} , and Cu-K α radiation was selected by using a graphite monochromator ($\lambda=1.5406 \text{ \AA}$). To prepare the samples, an aliquot of the suspension was dried at room temperature until solvent was evaporated. XRD provides information about the iron oxide phase of the nanoparticles and its crystal size (D_{XRD}). D_{XRD} was calculated from the broadening of the (311) reflection of the spinel structure following standard procedures.

Fe K-edge XAS experiments were performed at the beamline BL39XU of the SPring-8 Facility. XANES spectra were recorded at room temperature in the transmission mode and by using a Si(220) monochromator. The energy of the absorption spectra was calibrated by measuring the XANES of a Fe metal foil. For the measurements, homogeneous layers of the powdered samples were made by spreading fine powders of the material onto an adhesive tape. Thickness and homogeneity of the samples were optimized to obtain the best signal-to-noise ratio. XANES spectra were recorded on the nanoparticles and on a series of bulk iron oxide references: Fe_3O_4 (magnetite), $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ (hematite), $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ (maghemite), FeO(OH) (goethite), ferrihydrite, FeO (wüstite) and FeCO_3 (siderite). The absorption spectra were analyzed according to standard procedures⁶⁰ by using the ATHENA program package.⁶¹ It should be noted that these measurements are in perfect agreement with previous test measurements performed at the BM25A SpLine beamline of the ESRF. No modification of the XAS spectra, other than the signal to noise ratio and energy resolution, has been found on the same specimens measured at the initial run and up to three years later, neither in different specimens prepared from the same sample. This indicates that the observed properties are intrinsic and stable in time, i.e. no time-dependent oxidation has been observed. It should be also noted that our XANES measurements performed on the bulk reference oxides perfectly agree with those previously reported.^{37,43,44} In addition, Fe $L_{2,3}$ -edge XAS and

XMCD measurements on samples M9D and M18D were performed at the beamline 4ID-C of the Advanced Photon Source at Argonne National Laboratory. XMCD spectra were recorded in the TEY mode at $T = 7$ K and under the action of an applied magnetic field ($H = \pm 1$ T and ± 3 T). For the measurements, samples were prepared as pellets of homogeneous fine powders of the materials slightly diluted in BN (boron nitride). The pellets were mounted on the sample holder by using carbon tape.

The computation of the Fe K-edge XANES spectra was carried out using the multiple-scattering program CONTINUUM,⁶² included in the MXAN program package.⁶³ A complete discussion of the procedure can be found elsewhere.^{64–66} The potential for the different atomic clusters was approximated by a set of spherically averaged muffin-tin (MT) potentials built by following the standard Mattheis' prescription. The muffin-tin radii were determined following the Norman's criterion. During the computations special attention has been paid to determine the best choice for the overlapping factor between the muffin-tin spheres and for the exchange and correlation part of the final state potential.^{67–69} We have found that the best agreement between the computations and the experimental spectra is obtained by using an overlapping factor of 1% and the Dirac-Hara ECP potential, in agreement to previous works for transition metal oxides and related compounds.^{69–73} It should be stressed that no free parameter has been used during the calculations. The theoretically calculated spectra have been directly compared to the experimental XANES spectrum i.e., no fitting procedure has been used. The assessment of the quality of the theoretical computations is based on the correct reproduction of the shape and energy position of the different spectral features and of their relative energy separation and the intensity ratio. In all the cases, the theoretical spectra have been convoluted with a Lorentzian shape function to account for the core-hole lifetime⁷⁴ and the experimental resolution.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1: (Color online) XRD patterns of samples synthesized by different methods.

Characteristic X-ray diffractograms, evidencing the broadening of the peaks as crystal size decreases, are reported in Fig. 1. The crystallite sizes, (D_{XRD}), calculated from Scherrer's equation are summarized in Table 1. Representative TEM images of the nanoparticles synthesized by the three different methods described above are shown in Fig. 2. Comparison of particles obtained by

coprecipitation (M7) and thermal decomposition (M7D) shows that the latter are more spherical and regular in shape and, in addition, they are isolated from each other by an oleic acid capping layer. Sample M31, obtained by precipitation in aqueous media, consists on large particles that are highly aggregated due to the high dipolar interactions.

Table 1: Crystallite size XRD (D_{XRD}) and physical particle size (D_{TEM}) of the synthesized nanoparticles determined by XRD and TEM, respectively. w , the standard deviation of $\log D_{TEM}$ is an indicator of the degree of polydispersity.

Method	Sample	D_{XRD} (nm)	D_{TEM} (nm)	w (± 0.02)
Coprecipitation	M4	4.3 ± 0.2	4.8	0.17
	M6	6.8 ± 0.3	6.6	0.26
	M7	7.1 ± 0.3	5.8	0.23
Precipitation in aq. media	M29	29 ± 2	33	0.21
	M31	31 ± 2	42	0.27
Thermal decomposition	M7D	7.2 ± 0.5	6.8	0.14
	M9D	9.4 ± 0.4		
	M12D	11.5 ± 0.5		
Oxidation treatment	M18D	18 ± 1	18	0.21
	G7D	7.8 ± 0.2		
	G29	29 ± 2		
	G31	31 ± 2		

Fe $L_{2,3}$ -edge XAS and XMCD characterization.

The Fe $L_{2,3}$ -edges XAS and XMCD spectra recorded on the nanoparticles are reported in Fig. 3. For the sake of comparison the XAS and XMCD spectra of reference bulk samples are also displayed.^{75,76} The Fe $L_{2,3}$ -edge XAS and XMCD spectra of our samples are similar to those previously reported in similar systems.^{29,35} The XMCD spectra show the characteristic spectral profile of both magnetite and maghemite, i.e. the occurrence of three main peaks with negative (n_1), positive (p_2) and negative (n_3) intensity as energy increases. These peaks and their relative intensities

Figure 2: (Color online) Representative TEM images of iron oxide nanoparticles synthesized by different methods: (from left to right) sample M7 (coprecipitation); sample M7D (thermal decomposition) and M29 (precipitation in aqueous media). In the bottom panel an enlarged TEM image and size-distribution graph for the M7D sample are shown.

are typically accounted for in terms of the site occupancies of the Fe cations in the spinel structure ($\text{Fe}^{2+}\text{-O}_h$, $\text{Fe}^{3+}\text{-T}_d$ and $\text{Fe}^{3+}\text{-O}_h$).^{27,27,31,77-81}

Starting from the fair agreement between multiplet calculations and experimental XMCD on bulk iron oxides^{27,28} the XMCD of iron oxides NPs are often modeled by a linear combination of the three aforesaid Fe contributions. Following this method Park *et al.* characterized monodisperse iron oxide nanocrystals as a mixture of magnetite and maghemite in the form $(\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3)_{1-x}(\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4)_x$ whose relative amounts vary as a function of the NPs size.²⁹ In our case, the most significant difference in the XMCD of both M9D and M18D compounds and those of magnetite and maghemite lies in the relative intensity of the negative n_1 and n_3 peaks: the n_1/n_3 intensity ratio is ~ 0.8 , while it is ~ 0.4 and 1.5 for maghemite and magnetite, respectively. If one considers that these oxide nanocrystals corresponds to the proposed $(\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3)_{1-x}(\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4)_x$ mixture,²⁹ we find a significant amount of maghemite in the samples, $\sim 70\%$, in agreement with previous findings.³⁵ However, as well as the n_1/n_3 ratio coincides for both M9D and M18D samples the overall amplitude of the XMCD signals of the M18D is decreased by a ~ 1.2 factor with respect to that of the M9D sample. The picture emerging from the comparison of the overall intensity of the XMCD data is that the iron magnetic moment in sample M18D significantly decreases as compared with that of the M9D one, which is difficult to reconcile with the existence of the same mixture of bulk-like magnetite and maghemite for the two compounds (same n_1/n_3 ratio). If we take into account that the intensity of the white line of the M18D XAS spectrum (after normalization to the absorption edge jump) is $\sim 20\%$ higher than that obtained in the M9D, then the difference between the iron magnetic moment that one obtains by applying sum rules for M9D and M18D is even larger.^{82,83} In addition, if the increase in this white line intensity is simply addressed to the enhancement of the number of 3d holes in the Fe 3d band, the existence of the same mixture of bulk-like magnetite and maghemite for the two compounds is not a consistent conclusion.

Figure 3: (Color online) a) Comparison of the Fe $L_{2,3}$ -edges XAS and XMCD spectra recorded for M9D and M18D samples. b) Comparison of the Fe $L_{2,3}$ -edges XAS and XMCD spectra of reference bulk samples (adapted from Kim *et al.*⁷⁵ and Chang *et al.*,⁷⁶ respectively).

We would like to point out in this respect an experimental result that has deserved, to our knowledge, little attention in the past. As previously discussed, the XMCD spectra of nominal magnetite/maghemite NPs can be reasonably reproduced by a linear addition of the XMCD spectra of bulk magnetite and maghemite. However, the same does not hold for the XAS spectra. The XAS spectra of nominal magnetite and maghemite NPs show a sharp peak (A) in the absorption spectra that is not present in the spectra on the bulk references.^{29,35,46,75,76} As a consequence, contrary to the XMCD, the XAS spectra of nominal magnetite/maghemite NPs can not be reproduced by a linear addition of the XAS spectra of bulk magnetite and maghemite. Indeed, this spectral profile with a marked A peak resembles that found in the case of antiferromagnetic α - Fe_2O_3 , $\text{FeO}(\text{OH})$ or ferrihydrite oxides rather than those of magnetite or maghemite.^{46,84,85} Therefore, while the experimental Fe $L_{2,3}$ -edge XMCD spectra are compatible with the the proposed $(\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3)_{1-x}(\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4)_x$ scheme,²⁹ the same does not hold for the XAS spectra. In principle, the apparent contradiction between XMCD and XAS data might be reconciled by considering the presence of antiferromag-

netic oxides in the materials that should modify the XAS lineshape but not the XMCD one. If this was the case, the quantitative analysis of the XMCD spectra should be seriously concerned as the normalization of the signal and, consequently, the estimate of the Fe magnetic moment derived by applying the sum rules^{82,83} would be modified. However, attempts of reproducing the experimental XAS spectra (especially regarding the intensity of peak A) as a linear combination of bulk-like reference ones, as made for the XMCD spectra, yields that the relative amount of the AFM oxides should be large enough to be detected by macroscopic tools, contrary to the experimental observations.

All in all these results show that as far as the Fe $L_{2,3}$ -edge absorption is dictated by the valence and point symmetry of the absorbing sites the overall line shape of all these iron oxides are similar, which makes complicated to identify, beyond the $Fe^{2+}:Fe^{3+}$ ratio,^{25,26} the relative amount of the oxide phases present in the material. Consequently, the Fe $L_{2,3}$ -edge absorption alone is not able to provide an accurate structural determination in these cases in which a mixture of non-stoichiometric and/or stoichiometric iron oxides might be present. Alternatively, another way of describing the observed experimental trend is to consider the partial oxidation of magnetite, in the form $Fe_{3-\delta}O_4$, allowing the appearance of vacancies in the spinel octahedral sites.^{77,86,87} The oxidation of magnetite means a decrease of Fe^{2+} in octahedral sites, that is compensated by a slight increase in the occupancy of the octahedral sites by Fe^{3+} . The concomitant modification of the crystal field parameters may result in the shift of the energies of the absorption peaks^{27,76,88} and, consequently, structural determinations based in the weighted addition of end-members spectra could be affected.

Figure 4: (color online) (a) Comparison of the experimental Fe K-edge XANES spectra of several iron oxide bulk references. (b) Detailed comparison of the experimental Fe K-edge XANES spectra of Fe_3O_4 and $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ bulk references.

Fe K-edge XANES characterization.

As we have discussed before, when studying the physiochemical properties of nominal magnetite NPs it is not a trivial problem to determine if these systems are single or multiphase systems, and if the different components can be regarded as well defined, stoichiometric, bulk-like oxides or, on the contrary, they consist of non-stoichiometric oxides. The Fe $L_{2,3}$ -edges XAS and XMCD experimental evidences suggest the occurrence of non stoichiometric oxides, as $Fe_{3-\delta}O_4$, in which the structural arrangements at the Fe sites will be modified with respect to those found in bulk-like iron oxides. However, an unambiguous determination of these structural modification is still missing. Aimed to solve this question we have extended our study to the Fe K-edge, which shows higher sensitivity to the oxidation state and structural details than the Fe $L_{2,3}$ -edge. This is illustrated in Fig. 4 where the XANES spectra of several iron oxide bulk references are shown. Contrary to the Fe $L_{2,3}$ -edge case, the Fe K-edge spectral shape is clearly different for all the references considered, reflecting the sensitivity of the Fe K-edge absorption to the geometrical details of the absorbing site.

In particular, magnetite and maghemite show quite different XANES spectra, not only regarding the overall spectral shape but also concerning the edge position, see Fig. 4(b). The energy shift of the absorption threshold is due to the different Fe-O bond lengths (the shorter the interatomic distance, the higher the edge energy) which gives a hint on the different oxidation state of the Fe ions (Fe^{2+} and Fe^{3+}). Consequently, the chemical sensitivity of XANES is strongly influenced by the local geometry, so that empirical correlations between formal charge state and edge shifts are primarily mediated through changes in bond lengths.^{65,89-93} As a result it is not so much the valence itself, but more the resulting metal-oxygen distances that determine the edge energy in 3d oxides (see also the Supporting Information for further explanation).

The comparison of the Fe K-edge XANES spectra of all the studied samples, together with

Figure 5: (color online) (a) Comparison of the experimental Fe K-edge XANES spectra of nanoparticles synthesized by thermal decomposition (M7D , M9D, M12D and M18D) and sample G7D. (b) Detailed comparison of the experimental Fe K-edge XANES spectra of samples M9D, M12D and M18D with those of Fe_3O_4 and $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ bulk references. (c) Same as above in the case of samples M7D and G7D.

those of Fe_3O_4 and $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ bulk references are reported in Figs. 5, 6, and 7. From these figures it is clear that none of the studied NPs display the characteristic XANES profile of bulk magnetite. The larger samples ($\phi \geq 9$ nm) display a XANES spectra intermediate between those of the magnetite and maghemite bulk references. The smaller NPs ($\phi < 9$ nm) display a XANES profile similar to that of bulk maghemite, but the white lines are less intense and reach their maximum at lower energies. From these comparisons we can conclude that none of the nanoparticles show a single-phase bulk magnetite or maghemite structure, independently of the sample synthesis method. These results are in agreement with the Fe $L_{2,3}$ -edges XAS and XMCD results reported in the precedent section. This is of particular significance in the case of samples M9D and M18D for which the Fe K-edge absorption reveals significant differences, associated to a different structural arrangement. These structural effects were hindered to the Fe $L_{2,3}$ -edge XAS and XMCD probes, which poses serious doubts on the reliability of the results obtained from a simple fingerprint XMCD analysis of their magnetic properties. Regarding the differences and similarities in the NPs XANES spectra, it is worth noting that all the samples with $\phi \geq 12$ nm display a XANES profile nearly identical, irrespective of the sample synthesis method or whether they undergone an extra oxidation process, see Fig 6(c) and Fig 7(a).

Once the hypothesis of a single bulk-like phase has been disregarded, the next step is to explore the possibility of a $\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4@ \gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ core-shell structure. To this end, we have checked if the NPs XANES spectra can be accounted for as a weighted sum of the experimental spectra of both Fe_3O_4 and $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ bulk references. The comparisons are displayed in Fig. 8 and Fig. 9. As a common result we have found that none of the experimental spectra can be fully described as a linear combination of the spectra of the bulk references, i.e. it is not possible to find a weighted sum that simultaneously reproduces both the edge position and the white line (shape and position). For the smaller samples, $\phi < 9$ nm, the edge position is well reproduced by the weighted addition

Figure 6: (color online) (a) Detailed comparison of the experimental Fe K-edge XANES spectra of samples synthesized by coprecipitation (M4 and M7) with those of Fe₃O₄ and γ-Fe₂O₃ bulk references. (b) Same as above in the case of samples synthesized by precipitation in aqueous media (M29 and M31). (c) Same as above in the case of samples M31 and G31.

Figure 7: (color online) (a) Detailed comparison of the experimental Fe K-edge XANES spectra of samples M18D and M31 with those of the Fe_3O_4 and $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ bulk references. (b) Same as above in the case of samples M4 and G29.

of the spectra in the form 10% (7%) Fe_3O_4 + 90% (93%) of $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ ($\pm 10\%$, depending on the sample, see Fig. 8). On the other hand, the experimental white line lies between those of the 40%-60% (30%-70%) and 50%-50% (40%-60%) relative magnetite-maghemite weighted spectra (see Fig. 8). It should be noted that we are just adding normalized XANES spectra which corresponds to the absorption per Fe atom. Hence, the percentages used in the weighted sums refer to the XANES spectra and not to the Fe molar weight of each compound, which are indicated by the quantities in parentheses.

For the larger samples, $\phi \geq 9$ nm, see Fig. 9, the edge position is well reproduced by the weighted addition 40% Fe_3O_4 + 60% $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ (30%-70%), being 50%-50% (40%-60%) for M9D; however, there is no linear combination able to reproduce the shape of the white line. A $\sim 70\%$ of magnetite is necessary to reproduce the energy position of the maximum, but both the height and the shape of the corresponding white line are quite different from those of the experimental spectra (see Fig. 9).

These results clearly show that the NPs XANES spectra can not be seen as a weighted sum of the experimental spectra of both Fe_3O_4 and $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ bulk references. For the sake of completeness we have also studied a possible occurrence of other bulk iron oxides in the samples. In Fig. 10(a) we have compared the experimental spectrum of M18D (representative of the larger samples) with those of several bulk references including both goethite and ferrihydrite. The XANES spectra of these antiferromagnetic oxides display a threshold position close to that of maghemite but, at the same time, a white line broader and shifted to lower energy, resembling, to some extent, the experimental spectrum of the larger samples. However, as shown in Fig. 10(b), the inclusion of these antiferromagnetic phases does not significantly improve the overall spectral shape and, in particular, the white-line region. For the smaller samples, the inclusion of antiferromagnetic oxides does not improve either the agreement between the experimental spectra and the weighted sums,

Figure 8: (color online) (a) Comparison of the experimental Fe K-edge XANES spectra of the G7D sample and the weighted sums of the experimental spectra of Fe_3O_4 and $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ bulk references. (b) Comparison of the experimental Fe K-edge XANES spectra of the M7 sample and the weighted sums that better reproduced the edge and maximum positions, 50 and 20% of Fe_3O_4 , respectively (see text for details).

Figure 9: (color online) Comparison of the experimental Fe K-edge XANES spectra of the M31 sample and the weighted sums of the experimental spectra of Fe₃O₄ and γ-Fe₂O₃ bulk references. Inset: Comparison of the experimental Fe K-edge XANES spectra of the M31 sample and the weighted sums that better reproduced the edge and maximum positions, 40 and 80% of Fe₃O₄, respectively (see text for details).

see Fig. 10(c).

All these results clearly indicate that the experimental spectra are not well reproduced by any linear combination of the XANES spectra of Fe₃O₄ and γ-Fe₂O₃ bulk references, even taking into account other oxides as goethite or ferrihydrite. The failure of this hypothesis reflects the inadequacy of considering the NPs as bulk-based materials, i.e. that stoichiometric bulk-like oxides can grow and coexist separately in the confined space of the NP. It should be noted in this respect that the present results cast serious doubts regarding the gradual increase of the magnetite content as the particle size does in the proposed magnetite-maghemite core-shell model. As shown in Fig. 11, the relative amount of magnetite needed to account for the edge or white-line position of the Fe K-edge spectra of nanoparticles of increasing size "saturates" for $\phi \geq 12$ nm, while a linear increase is expected according to the magnetite-maghemite core-shell model.

Figure 10: (color online) Comparison of the experimental Fe *K*-edge XANES spectra of the M18D and M9D samples and the weighted sums of the experimental spectra of bulk Fe_3O_4 , $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$, FeO(OH) and ferrihydrite (Fh).

Figure 11: (color online) Dependence on the nanoparticle size of the relative amount ($\pm 5\%$) of magnetite XANES in the weighted sum of the experimental spectra of Fe_3O_4 and $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ bulk references needed to match the energy position of both the edge and the white of the Fe K-edge experimental spectra. (see text for details) .

The fact that the XAS spectrum remains basically invariable for NPs with $\phi \geq 12$ nm implies that the local structural arrangement of Fe does not depend on the NPs size as expected for a core/shell scheme, and supports the existence of a single non-stoichiometric phase. Similarly, our results show that for a given particle size, see for instance M7 *vs.* M7D, the local structural arrangement of Fe depends little on the synthesis method (in principle affecting the oxidation rate). It should be noted in this respect that, within the core-shell scenario, samples obtained by thermal decomposition should exhibit, in principle, a greater content of magnetite because the reaction is carried out in organic media in the presence of hexadecanediol⁹⁴ and the oleic acid prevents from oxidation.⁵⁴ Similarly, for those samples subjected to further oxidation, a majority maghemite phase should be expected, contrary to the experimental results. All these results suggest that a single phase is developed inside the NPs during the synthesis process. This phase is unaffected by further oxidation processes and its structural details are mainly determined by steric effects; that

is, the partial oxidation of the nominal magnetite NPs mainly comes from a larger disorder on the octahedral sub-network allowing the appearance of vacancies in the spinel octahedral sites. This disorder, caused by the size constrain, leads to the modification of the structural arrangements at the Fe sites with respect to those found in bulk-like iron oxides. This new, intermediate, phase can be seen as a mixture of "structurally-adapted" magnetite and maghemite oxides, in such a way that magnetite and maghemite rearrange their crystallographic structure in order to get the same crystal cell parameter, being the size of the NPs which determines the variation of the parameter cell and the distribution of the vacancies. Hence, we have explored the possibility that the formed Fe oxide grows in a single crystal structure with a cell parameter lying in between those of the pure stoichiometric magnetite and maghemite oxides. Because no reference spectra exist for this purpose we have investigated this possibility with *ab-initio* theoretical calculations of the Fe K-edge XANES. We have firstly performed the computations for the bulk-like structures and, in a second step, we have studied the effect of modifying the cell parameters into the XANES spectra of both Fe_3O_4 and $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ bulk oxides.

Figure 12: (color online) Comparison between the experimental Fe K-edge of $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ (red, squares), $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ (blue, \circ) and Fe_3O_4 (green, \bullet) and the computations performed by using the Dirac-Hara ECP (solid line). The dashed lines correspond to the computations performed by using the *complex* Dirac-Hara ECP (see text for details).

Figure 13: (color online) Comparison between the experimental Fe K-edge of $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ (black square), Fe_3O_4 (red, \bullet) and sample M31 (green, \circ), and the results of the theoretical computations performed for the original magnetite (red, dots) and maghemite (black, dash) clusters and for those (green, solid line) in which the cell parameter has been varied (see text for details).

The result of the calculations performed for the reference bulk oxides are shown Fig. 12 (see the Supplementary Information for computational details). In all cases the computations reproduce not only the overall experimental spectral shape but also the relative intensity of the spectral features as well as their relative energy separation. In addition, computations displayed on an unique energy scale reproduce the characteristic edge shift associated to the different interatomic distances of these oxides. Now we have explored the possibility that the formed Fe oxide grows in a single crystal structure with a cell parameter lying in between those of the pure stoichiometric magnetite and maghemite oxides. If this is the case not only the structural arrangements at the Fe sites but also the distribution of the Fe^{2+} and Fe^{3+} ions, including vacancies, would slightly depart from those of bulk Fe_3O_4 and $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ stoichiometric iron oxides. Therefore we have performed the calculations by considered it as an intermediate structure between Fe_3O_4 and $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ regarding both the structural and electronic parameters. To this end we have carried out the same class of computations for Fe_3O_4 and $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ clusters in which the cell parameter have been progressively modified up to reach 8.364 \AA , i.e. the average of those of the pure magnetite and maghemite

compounds. The modification of the cell parameter leads to the overall shift of the spectra without modifying the spectral shape. When decreasing the cell parameter of Fe_3O_4 , i.e. the Fe-O interatomic distance, the main absorption peak shifts to higher energies while the contrary occurs for $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ in which the cell parameter is being increased. As a result, when the computation is performed for both magnetite and maghemite clusters by imposing the same (averaged) cell parameter the main peak lies in the middle between those of the unmodified clusters. Fig. 13 shows the comparison of the computations performed for the original magnetite and maghemite clusters and the 50% weighted sum⁹⁵ of the spectra computed for the clusters modified as detailed above. The results are compared to the experimental spectra of both bulk Fe_3O_4 and $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ and of representative M31 sample. The computations reproduce both the experimental energy shift of the different spectral features as well as the relative variation of the intensity of main absorption line. The good agreement between the experimental and theoretical spectra strongly supports that the Fe oxide grows in the NPs as a single spinel structure whose structural parameters and $\text{Fe}^{2+}/\text{Fe}^{3+}$ ratio differs from those of bulk magnetite and maghemite.

Finally, we have taken advantage of the results of the theoretical computations to apply a similar procedure to the experimental spectra. In this way we have applied the weighting procedure of the XANES spectra of the bulk magnetite and maghemite references but shifting their energy scale prior addition, i.e. simulating to some extent their expected variation upon modification of the structural parameters.⁹⁵ The comparison to the experimental spectra, reported in Fig. 14, shows an excellent agreement among the experimental spectra and the calculated ones. In the case of the larger samples good agreement is obtained by a 50% weighting of the Fe_3O_4 and $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ after shifting them by $\Delta E = \pm 0.75$ or ± 1 eV. As discussed above this procedure is an empirical way of taking into account the modification of the interatomic distances. Provided that the cell parameters of magnetite and maghemite are 8.394 and 8.334 Å, respectively, the positive shift applies for

Figure 14: (color online) (a) Fe K-edge XANES spectra of M31 (\circ) together the best fit obtained with the weighted sums of the displaced references: 50% Fe_3O_4 + 50% $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ (red, \bullet), 50% Fe_3O_4 ($\Delta E = 1$ eV) + 50% $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ ($\Delta E = -1$ eV) (blue, \blacksquare), 50% Fe_3O_4 + 50% $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ ($\Delta E = -2.5$ eV) (green, \blacktriangle), 30% Fe_3O_4 + 70% $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ ($\Delta E = -0.5$ eV) (magenta, \blacklozenge). (b) Same as above in the case of the M4 sample (black, \circ): 20% Fe_3O_4 + 80% $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ (red, \bullet), 20% Fe_3O_4 ($\Delta E = 1$ eV) + 80% $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ ($\Delta E = -1$ eV) (blue, \blacksquare), 20% Fe_3O_4 + 80% $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ ($\Delta E = -2.5$ eV) (green, \blacktriangle), 20% Fe_3O_4 + 80% $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ ($\Delta E = -0.5$ eV) (magenta, \blacklozenge).

magnetite, i.e. decreasing the Fe-O distance, and the negative to maghemite, i.e. increasing the bond length. In the case of the smaller samples the best fit is obtained by applying a $\Delta E = 1.5$ eV for magnetite reference spectra and $\Delta E = -0.5$ eV for the maghemite one, which agrees with the fact that the experimental edge position (and consequently the bond length) is closer to maghemite. As a final test we have also considered the possibility of a core-shell arrangement where the core corresponds to bulk-like magnetite and the shell to "oxidized" magnetite. In this case the weighting of the reference spectra should be made without shifting the energy of the Fe_3O_4 one. No good agreement with the experimental spectra is obtained by following this procedure.

The results obtained in this work support the existence of a single "non-stoichiometric" phase in these nominal magnetite nanoparticles. None of the nanoparticles show a single-phase bulk magnetite or maghemite structure, independently of the sample synthesis method. Moreover, the XAS spectra cannot be accounted for in terms of a mixture of bulk-like iron oxides. The fact that no modification of the Fe K-edge XANES is observed between samples grown by different procedures (including extra oxidation) suggests that the local structural arrangement of Fe, and therefore its related structural disorder, depends mainly on the NPs size. This dependence would not be linear, but range-defined. In other words, the particle size plays the main role into determining the structural properties of the NPs: the modification of the interatomic distances, the ratio of Fe ions in different electronic state, and the crystal field parameters, which in turn determine other properties.

Summary and Conclusions

In this work we propose a new approach to determine the structure of Fe oxide NPs by using the Fe K-edge X-ray absorption near edge spectroscopy. To this end, we have performed a detailed XANES study at the Fe K- and $L_{2,3}$ -edges on nominal magnetite nanoparticles synthesized by

different methods. In addition, X-ray magnetic circular dichroism was recorded at the Fe $L_{2,3}$ -edges in selected samples. Our main objective is to determine if the nominal Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles are single or multiphase systems, as well as the nature of these phases.

We have verified that the Fe $L_{2,3}$ -edge absorption alone is not able to determine the structure of nanosized magnetite NPs. As far as the Fe $L_{2,3}$ -edge absorption is dictated by the valence and point symmetry of the absorbing sites, the overall line shape of all the iron oxides is similar, making complicated to identify the relative amount of the oxide phases present in the material. In contrast, the Fe K-edge spectral shape is clearly different for all the references considered, reflecting the high sensitivity of the Fe K-edge absorption to the geometrical details of the absorbing site. Another critical advantage of using the Fe K-edge absorption for this purpose is that it probes the whole NPs, whereas the probing depth of the Fe $L_{2,3}$ -edge absorption is only ~ 45 Å in iron oxides, which limits its accuracy to evaluate possible surface/volume effects.

The analysis of the XAS data recorded at both Fe K- and $L_{2,3}$ -edges indicates that the experimental spectra are not well reproduced by any linear combination of the absorption spectra of Fe_3O_4 and γ - Fe_2O_3 bulk references, even taking into account other oxides as goethite or ferrihydrite. In other words, none of the synthesized NPs can be identified as a mixture of stoichiometric bulk-like iron oxides, independently of the sample synthesis method or whether they undergone an extra oxidation process. The failure of this hypothesis reflects the inadequacy of considering the NPs as bulk-based materials, i.e. that stoichiometric bulk-like oxides can grow and coexist separately in the confined space of the NP.

The analysis of the Fe K-edge spectra indicates that the local structural arrangement of Fe does not depend on the NPs size as expected for a core/shell scheme. Likewise, we can conclude that the local structural arrangement of Fe is very stable and it depends little on the synthesis method (in principle affecting the oxidation rate) and that it does not change when the NPs are subjected

to a further oxidation (in this case, a majority maghemite phase should be expected, contrary to the experimental results). Moreover, our results indicate that the synthesis of the Fe_3O_4 magnetite nanoparticles leads to the growing of a single phase non stoichiometric oxide whose crystal structure possesses a cell parameter lying in between those of the pure stoichiometric magnetite and maghemite oxides.

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Supplementary Information

Theoretical computation of Fe K-edge XANES spectra.

The initial computations have been made for magnetite, maghemite and hematite. To this aim we have built-up clusters that include all the atoms within the first 7.5 Å around the photoabsorber by using the structural parameters reported in the literature: α -Fe₂O₃ ($a = 5.038$ Å, $c = 13.772$ Å);⁹⁷ γ -Fe₂O₃ ($a = 8.334$ Å);⁹⁸ Fe₃O₄ ($a = 8.3941$ Å).⁹⁹ In Fe₃O₄ and γ -Fe₂O₃, Fe occupies two different crystallographic positions (8a) and (16d). Consequently, the computation of the absorption cross section has to be performed separately for Fe absorbing atoms occupying both crystallographic sites; the final XANES spectrum is obtained by adding both contributions weighted by the crystallographic occupancy.

Throughout this work we have always followed the same computational procedure. First, we have determined the minimum size of the cluster needed to reproduce all the spectral features. This is made by adding progressively coordination shells surrounding the absorbing atom until convergence is obtained, i.e. the addition of further shells do not lead to the modification of the relative energy separation and intensity of the spectral features or to the appearance of new ones. In a second step we have checked the influence of the overlapping factor among the muffin-tin spheres used to built up the scattering potential into the reproduction of the experimental XANES spectra. Moreover, we have also studied the effect of modifying the value of the maximum angular momentum quantum number, l_{max} , needed to account for the experimental absorption spectrum in the first ~ 50 eVs. Last but not least we have studied the best choice of the exchange and correlation part of the final state potential (ECP) to reproduce not only the spectral shape but also the intensity of the computed spectral features and their relative energy separation. To this end we have performed the computations by using (i) the energy dependent Hedin-Lundqvist (HL) ECP potential, (ii) the energy dependent Dirac-Hara (DH) ECP potential, (iii) only the real part of the HL ECP (hereafter *real* HL) and (iv) by adding the imaginary part of the HL ECP to the Dirac-Hara one (hereafter *complex* Dirac-Hara). We have found that the best agreement between the computations and the experimental spectra is obtained by using an overlapping factor of 1% and the Dirac-Hara ECP potential, in agreement to previous works for transition metal oxides and related compounds,^{69–73} for which the use of complex potentials leads to the excessive damping of the main spectral features.

The initial computations have been made for magnetite, maghemite and hematite. The results of these computations are shown in Fig. 12 of the main text. In all the cases the agreement between the experimental spectra and the calculations is remarkable. Computations reproduce not only the overall spectral shape but also the relative intensity of the spectral features as well as their relative

energy separation. In addition, computations displayed on an unique energy scale reproduce the characteristic edge shift associated to the different interatomic distances of these oxides.

It should be noted in this regard that the energy scale of each computation is referred to its own muffin-tin potential. Therefore, it is necessary to correct the energy scale of the computed spectra in order to compare the calculations for the different compounds in a unique energy scale. In this way we can monitor the edge-shift associated to the structural modification, i.e. to the modification of the interatomic distances.^{65,90} This is of particular significance in the case of the XANES spectra of both magnetite and maghemite that show a different edge position (see Fig. 4b in the main text). The energy shift of the absorption threshold is due to the different Fe-O bond lengths (the shorter the interatomic distance, the higher the edge energy) which gives a hint on the different oxidation state of the Fe ions (Fe^{2+} and Fe^{3+}). Very often the edge position is used to derive quantitative estimates of the oxidation state of the absorbing atom. However, inferring the oxidation state from the edge position is not straightforward. In theory, K-edge XANES analysis can provide information on the valence of the 3d ion as well as its site symmetry and distortion. In this regard, despite the concept of valence is more and more questioned by physicists, a number of authors determined the valence of many ions (including 3d ions) by evaluating the "edge position" in the experimental XANES spectrum (considering the inflexion point in an edge jump, for instance). Unfortunately, the "edge energy" has never been recognized as a reliable measure of the valence of a probed ion by XANES methods, and different examples demonstrate that the position of the edge cannot always be used to determine the oxidation state.^{65,89–93} For instance, *Farges et al* have compared the Cr K-edge XANES spectra collected for model compounds, in which Cr is trivalent and octahedrally-coordinated to oxygen ligands. These comparisons show that the measure of the 3d-valence in the edge jump region cannot be reliable, and only the pre-edge region can reasonably be used to derive valence information.^{89,90} Consequently, the chemical sensitivity of XANES is

strongly influenced by the local geometry, so that empirical correlations between formal charge state and edge shifts are primarily mediated through changes in bond lengths.⁹¹ As a result it is not so much the valence itself, but more the resulting metal-oxygen distances that determine the edge energy in 3d oxides.

Graphic for TOC

Figure 15: Graphic TOC.